

THE ROLE OF FINTECH IN ADVANCING SUSTAINABILITY: A BIBLIOMETRIC STUDY AND FUTURE RESEARCH AGENDA

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Abstract

Fintech is a technology-enabled financial solution that has implications for the future of the global financial system and has become a policy concern. The two main forces behind the present significant transition of the financial services sector are digitization and sustainability. This bibliometric analysis investigates the evolving landscape of research at the intersection of financial technology (fintech) and sustainability. By systematically examining publications, citations, and author networks, this study aims to identify key trends, influential works, and emerging areas within this interdisciplinary field. Utilizing the databases Scopus, we compile a comprehensive dataset of research articles and reviews from the past decade. Research activity has significantly increased, according to the data, as more people realize how fintech may help achieve the goals of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The influence of artificial intelligence on sustainable investment strategies, the usage of mobile banking to improve financial inclusion, and the significance of blockchain in promoting efficiency and transparency in green finance are some of the major themes that have been discovered. Co-citation and co-authorship network analyses uncover prominent researchers and collaborative clusters, highlighting the interdisciplinary nature of the field. Along with addressing gaps in the literature, the article makes recommendations for future research topics.

Keywords: Fintech, Sustainability, Bibliometric Analysis, Global Financial System, vos Viewer.

1. INTRODUCTION

Climate change is one of the most significant challenges to humanity, if not the most dangerous. Preventing the occurrence of critical levels, such as the one represented by a 2° Celsius increase above pre-industrial levels, would need sustainability (Arner et al., 2020; Atayah et al., 2023). Recent research indicates that if this threshold is exceeded, global warming could persist despite human attempts to reduce CO2 emissions (Steffen et al., 2018; Lisha, et al., 2023).

Nevertheless, social and economic imbalances, enormous national disparities, population growth that is outpacing access to basic necessities, and the fact that over one billion

people are considered to be multidimensional impoverished demonstrate that all actors—particularly governments and private agents—are susceptible to global pressures. (UNDP 2019; Arner et al., 2020; Rambaud, 2023; Vergara, et al., 2021). In the present instance, mobilizing substantial funds is essential to carrying out the necessary adjustments. Consequently, the banking industry has a great opportunity to provide financial solutions that promote the growth of sustainable finance and, as a result, coordinate their operations with a green and sustainable economy (Falcone, 2018; Rambaud, 2022).

Fintech describes an extensive variety of financial technologies that use advances in digital technology to transform traditional financial services and transactions. By offering creative solutions for sustainable mobility, fintech significantly contributes to the advancement of environmental sustainability in the framework of sustainable smart cities, intelligent energy management, green financing, and other issues. Fintech facilitates the implementation of data-driven tactics, efficient resource allocation, and effective public participation in environmentally friendly initiatives in communities (Awotunde et. al., 2021; Suryono et al., 2020).

Fintech minimizes the disparity between information and trade costs by bridging the gap between traditional finance and information technology in order to promote the connection of excess and deficit money (T. Muganyi 2021). Fintech makes investment more accessible to small investors by turning it into something more economical, useful, inclusive, and transparent and determining the amount of money they require. It has also contributed to the advancement of sustainable development by ensuring the availability of green money, reducing costs and information asymmetry, increasing efficiency, recognizing the value of the earth's resources, and offering realistic sustainable lifestyles. The growth of fintech has made sustainable finance possible (Yang 2021; R. Tao 2022; M.C. Udeagha et al., 2023).

The quick uptake of fintech solutions has had an impact on financial performance, which is a crucial indicator of the health and sustainability of financial institutions. Numerous organizations have experienced improved financial results as a result of these technologies' simpler processes, lower costs, and improved customer experiences. Yet, in order to guarantee stable development and long-term expansion of the financial system, the incorporation of fintech also calls for a reassessment of established business models and rules.

At the corporate, national, and international levels, sustainable finance—and especially climate-related finance—has gained importance in recent years. Nevertheless, to carry out the Paris Agreement and achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), significant yearly investments of at least \$3 trillion globally and \$1.4 trillion in developing countries are required (Schmidt-Traub 2021). As we embrace the era of technological advancement, multiple businesses are accepting and allocating resources towards novel technologies in order to address the demands of both society and the environment (Taneja et al., 2023).

Comparable to other industries, the finance industry is constantly changing due to the emergence of fintech technology. Fintech refers to the integration of financial technology employed to augment the effectiveness and efficiency of financial activities (Rodrigues et al., 2022). It is presumed that it is a developing field of finance that makes a substantial contribution. The most current developments in information technology tools, including big data, cloud computing, social computing, and the internet of things, are being effectively employed by this business.

In light of this, (Rehman et al., 2023) claim that the adoption of Fintech is hampered by its dual-edged character, which presents both advantages and threats. (Tamasiga et al., 2023) noted that the breadth of its adoption is constrained by its disruptive effect on the traditional ways that companies, and banking in particular, are conducted (Daud et al., 2022). The emergence of FinTech may help to blur the established traditional boundaries in theory and practice by enhancing the complex interaction between conventional and alternative finance.

Presenting a thorough bibliometric analysis of the corpus of research on sustainability, financial performance, and fintech advancements is the aim of this study. Through a review of the literature, our goal is to pinpoint important themes, significant studies, and developing fields of study. We can map the intellectual landscape of this multidisciplinary sector in a methodical way due to the bibliometric technique, which also provides comprehensive data on the relationship between fintech, financial performance, and sustainability. Over the past ten years, an increasing amount of bibliometric literature evaluations have been conducted with the objective of mapping the conceptual structure of FinTech. These reviews have concentrated on important factors, obstacles, prospects, and emerging trends (Caciatori , 2020; Nasir et al., 2021). A few studies have addressed the idea of "sustainable FinTech" as an example of FinTech that only addresses economic growth, as financial institutions place a high priority on promoting sustainable development. Fewer studies have looked at how FinTech and sustainability interact, as well as whether FinTech can promote sustainability (Chueca et al., 2021). To our understanding, no bibliometric analysis of past research on "Sustainable Financial Performance through Fintech" has been done. This study is the first that sheds light on this area of inquiry. By evaluating the most relevant fintech issues, this study contributes to the corpus of literature.

We seek to address the following research questions through our analysis:

- RQ1: What effects has fintech adoption had on financial performance in various industries and geographical areas?
- RQ2: Which keywords appear most frequently in papers that have been published?
- RQ3: Who are the most cited Authors and most cited documents?
- RQ4: What are the most often referenced studies about the connection between sustainability and fintech?
- RQ5: Provide a framework for and future directions of research.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

From 2008 to 2013, FinTech embarked on transforming traditional financial procedures, contributing to the financial industry the means to lower operating costs and achieve an extensive reach through innovations such as peer-to-peer lending platforms, internet banking, and mobile payments (Remoaldo, 2009). During this period, banks acquire the ability to access deprived populations through digital financial gadgets, improving efficiency and profitability while encouraging financial inclusion (Magnuson, 2018). The primary focus, however, was on financial performance rather than sustainability, with advancements aimed at enhancing customer service, reducing expenses, and accelerating transactions (Dadgar et al., 2013).

The significance of integrating sustainability into financial systems emerged as a key consideration inside the growing FinTech ecosystem (Arner, 2015). Industries transverse how FinTech could contribute to sustainable development by presenting products like green bonds and sustainable investments (Lee, 2015; Schueffel, 2016). Blockchain technology was initiated as a promising tool to upgrade accountability and transparency in sustainable finance, allowing tamper-proof tracking of green investments (Gomber, 2017).

Studies revealed that FinTech might increase stakeholder confidence in financial markets by facilitating traceability in ESG-related transactions (Dorfleitner, 2017). The emphasis moved towards integrating FinTech with green finance, as studies recognized the potential of electronic finance to support global climate goals (Leong, 2018). FinTech permits more efficient investments in green energy and other sustainable initiatives, with blockchain technology and AI-driven data analytics providing tools for examining the environmental impact of portfolios (UNDP 2019).

Additionally, online forums for green project financing were developed, making sustainable finance more accessible and encouraging greater public involvement in climate resilience efforts (Goldstein, 2019; Knewtson, 2020; Giglio, 2021; Bollaert et al., 2021). Beginning in 2021, researchers turned their attention to executive frameworks needed to ensure the success of sustainable FinTech (Allen, 2021; Berg et al., 2022).

Regulators in several regions began establishing suggestions to support sustainable financing while maintaining financial stability, recognizing that powerful regulations were critical to preventing green washing and securing digital banking that coheres to ESG standards (Khalil, 2023; Wang et al., 2023). For example, the European Union introduced the Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation (SFDR) and the classifying Regulation to ensure transparency and liability in digital finance platforms' sustainability claims (Wang, 2023).

Clear regulatory frameworks were picked out as essential for boosting FinTech's positive impact on sustainable finance while securing misuse for unethical or unsustainable purposes (Macchiavello, 2022; Mertzanis et al., 2023). Innovations such as peer-to-peer lending and digital banking have made financial services more accessible to deprived communities, especially in developing nations (Taherdoost, 2023; Cumming et

al., 2023). These technological advancements enable low-income individuals to interact with formal financial institutions, thereby reducing poverty and encouraging economic equality (Sampat, 2024). Inclusive digital finance has become an important tool for advancing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by addressing social justice and poverty elevation. Moreover, the application of advanced digital technologies, including artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning, is driving development in sustainability outcomes within finance (Subramanian, 2023; Harsono, 2024; Alt et al., 2024).

Table 1: Theories discussed in the context of FinTech and sustainability using findings from past research.

Theory	Article	Description
Legitimacy Theory (Toumi et al.,2023)	The role of Fintech firms' sustainability during the COVID-19 period (2023)	The theory explains that to employ legitimacy, institutions should aim to operate within the restraints and conventions of their particular communities, aligning their operations with communal standards.
Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)(Davis,et al.,1989)	Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology.	This theory explains how customers accept and utilize technology, having stress on perceived utility and clarity of use as the major elements determining adoption.
Carbon Equivalence Principle (CEP)(Ellerman et al., 2003)	Absolute vs. intensity-based emission caps.	This theory proposes that the carbon tracks of financial instruments be incorporated as a linked term sheet united with existing bank systems to ensure transparency in sustainability initiatives.
Stakeholder Theory (Freeman et al., 2010)	"Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach	This theory proposes that firms attain stakeholders' expectations, including consumers, employees, and communities, in order to attain long-term sustainability.
Institutional Theory (DiMaggio et al., 1983)	The iron cage revisited: Institutional isomorphism and collective rationality in organizational fields.	This investigates how organized contexts, such as norms, regulations, and practices, affect organizational development and FinTech adoption.
Dynamic Capabilities Theory (Teece et al., 1997)	Dynamic capabilities and strategic management.	The theory emphasizes the ability of an organization to alter and restructure internal and external means in response to quickly changing environments, such as sustainability problems in FinTech.

3. METHODOLOGY AND DATA

Data Collection and Methodology

The data for this study were retrieved from the SCOPUS database in July 2024. SCOPUS was selected as the primary source of data due to its status as one of the most widely recognized and frequently utilized databases for financial research analysis (Zupic and Cater, 2015; Donthu et al., 2021).

SCOPUS provides comprehensive coverage of peer-reviewed literature, ensuring high reliability and relevance for bibliometric studies. Bibliometric analysis, facilitated by computerized data processing, has been endorsed by academic and professional societies as an efficient tool to reduce human errors (Ellegaard and Wallin, 2015) and mitigate subjective bias in literature reviews (Zupic and Cater, 2015).

Bibliometric research offers unique opportunities to make valuable and original contributions to theory and practice through its rigorous and systematic approach (Mukherjee et al., 2022).

Search Strategy

The time span for data retrieval was set from 2015 to 2024, reflecting a decade of intensive research activity in the field. The search terms employed were: "fintech," OR "financial technology," AND "digital finance," AND "financial performance," AND "sustainability." These terms were used in conjunction with Boolean operators (e.g., AND/OR) to ensure comprehensive coverage.

The search query was structured to include these terms in the titles, abstracts, and/or keywords of the articles, with quotation marks used to preserve the exact phrases. The selection of keywords was informed by the authors' prior research, key references in the field, and their subject matter expertise.

Specifically, the baseline list of terms and concepts was derived from seminal works and relevant contributions by notable researchers (Gallego-Losada, 2023; Zou, 2023; Kumar, 2022). The search was conducted using SCOPUS' advanced options, targeting the keywords, abstract, and article title fields.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

To ensure academic rigor, only peer-reviewed journal articles were included in the analysis, with the search parameters refined to focus on specific subject areas: social sciences, business, management, accounting, economics, econometrics, and finance. The document types were restricted to journal articles, excluding non-peer-reviewed publications such as conference proceedings or book chapters.

The initial search yielded 185 works, which were independently reviewed by two researchers to evaluate their coherence and relevance to the study's objectives. Articles identified as inaccurate, inconsistent, or irrelevant were excluded, resulting in a final data set of 79 peer-reviewed journal articles.

Additional refinement steps, including filtering by publication time frame, subject area, source, and document type, were applied to enhance the reliability and precision of the data acquisition process.

This systematic approach ensures that the data-set reflects the most relevant and high-quality research contributions in the domains of financial technology, firm performance, and sustainability. Figure 1. shows the process flowchart.

Figure 1: Process flowchart

4. RESULTS

4.1 Analysis by country of publishing, prominent authors, journals, and publication growth

Table 2. data set offers a thorough examination of academic publications pertaining to a particular field of study from 2015 to 2024, demonstrating both substantial growth and collaborative efforts. The research domain has had an exceptional yearly growth rate of 37.87%, with 79 papers drawn from various publications and journals, demonstrating

rising scholarly production and interest. The relatively young average age of these documents—1.96 years—indicates that the subject is still relevant today and that new research has made a substantial contribution to the conversation.

With an average of 21.72 citations per document, these publications' impact and scholarly reach are demonstrated by their 5,410 references. Notably, 336 particular "author's keywords" and 284 keywords used as "keywords plus" indicate an extensive and complex vocabulary related to this field of research.

With 253 distinct writers contributing to the topic, the authorial structure shows a collaborative landscape; just six documents are single-authored. A significant worldwide interest in the subject is shown by the average of 3.3 co-authors per paper, with foreign co-authorships accounting for 37.97% of partnerships. The fact that every document in this data collection is an article highlights the content's scientific and analytical personality.

Table 2: Shows the main information taken from the Bibliometrix R Package

Description	Results
MAIN INFORMATION ABOUT DATA	
Timespan	2015:204
Sources (Journals, Books, etc)	40
Documents	79
Annual Growth Rate %	37.87
Document Average Age	1.96
Average citations per doc	21.72
References	5410
DOCUMENT CONTENTS	
Keywords Plus (ID)	284
Author's Keywords (DE)	336
AUTHORS	
Authors	253
Authors of single-authored docs	6
AUTHORS COLLABORATION	
Single-authored docs	6
Co-Authors per Doc	3.3
International co-authorships %	37.97
DOCUMENT TYPES	
article	79

4.2. Descriptive analysis of the collected documents

A) Documents Publication by year

Figure 2. shows how many articles addressing the connection between FinTech and sustainability were published between 2015 and 2024. Initially, from 2015 to 2017, the research output was minimal, indicating either low interest or an emerging field with limited scholarly attention. However, from 2018 onwards, a gradual increase in publications can be observed, particularly peaking in 2019. This suggests that the field began gaining traction during this period, likely due to increasing academic focus.

A significant surge occurred in 2020, with the number of publications rising sharply, possibly driven by external factors like global events that triggered heightened research activities. The upward trend continued through 2021, reaching its peak in 2022, marking this as the most productive year in terms of document output. This indicates that the field reached a high point of scholarly engagement, perhaps due to increased funding or the maturation of research.

However, in 2023 and 2024, there is a noticeable decline, though still higher than the initial years. This decrease suggests that the intense focus on the field may have begun to wane, potentially due to market saturation, the resolution of key research questions, or a shift in research priorities. Overall, the data reflect a field that experienced rapid growth followed by a tapering off, providing a clear bibliometric narrative of its rise, peak, and partial decline over the past decade.

The growing recognition of the significance of the connection between FinTech and sustainability principles at both the micro and macro levels is another driver contributing to the rise in publications in this field.

Figure 2: documents by publication year

B) Research Output by Country

Figure 3. shows the contributions to research by highlighting the number of articles published by different nations. With over nine papers, China tops the list and demonstrates its dominance in the dataset's research output. Following closely behind with about 7 and 6 documents, respectively, Malaysia and the UK demonstrate their substantial intellectual activity. Taiwan and Jordan both contribute significantly, with about five documents, indicating that they are active centers of study. Compared to the top contributors, India, Indonesia, Saudi Arabia, Italy, and Singapore have each published about four documents, which is a reasonable level of contribution.

Figure 3: Document by countries

4.3 Bibliometric Analysis

A) Keywords analysis

Co-word analysis is a bibliometric technique that investigates the relationships between ideas that appear together in keywords, abstracts, and titles. The advantage of this strategy is that the co-word can generate a field and structure.

The fact that words can have several meanings and structures is a disadvantage (Zupic & Cater, 2015). The basic idea behind co-word analysis is that words that appear often in documents might imply related meanings. Co-word analysis is a novel bibliometric technique that generates similarity metrics from actual words. (Zupi & Cater, 2015).

A total of 556 author keywords were identified, of which 21 of the most commonly occurring terms are displayed together with their frequency of occurrence on the map in Figure 4. The network visualisation draws attention to how the terms "fintech," "sustainability," and "finance" are related in current research.

As a significant core node, "sustainability" indicates that sustainable practices are a key priority in the context of financial technology and economic growth. Its frequent co-occurrence with other ideas further supports its relevance. The remaining terms indicate variations in the theme's interpretation across experts. Table 3. shows the key insights of keyword cluster.

Table 3: Keywords by cluster

S.no	Cluster	Keywords	Key insights
1	Sustainable Finance	Sustainability, green finance, green economy, digitization, perception, technology adoption, financial services	Focuses on the incorporation of sustainability in financial systems, highlighting digitization, adoption of green practices, and the role of technology in altering finance.
2	Fintech	Financial Systems, banking, sustainable finance, financial technology, decision making	Highlights how fintech is modifying traditional financial systems, carrying sustainability goals, and improving decision-making processes via advanced technologies.
3	Innovation in Finance	Financial technology, economic growth, investment, finance, environmental economics	Explores the intersection of technology and finance, highlighting the role of innovation in driving economic growth and labelling environmental and investment challenges.

Figure 4: Cartography with 5 minimum co-occurring keywords. Source: VOS viewer

B) Co - authorship analysis

In bibliometrics, co-authorship analysis is a technique used to examine authors' collaboration ties based on their combined publications. This kind of study aids in determining research on the networks, cooperation patterns, and composition of academic communities. This yielded 26 of the 45 countries (Figure 5). Global scientific relationships are demonstrated by this co-authorship network of nations. China, India, Germany, and Pakistan are all connected via the United Kingdom, which serves as a major centre. While Italy links to nations like South Korea and Azerbaijan, the network emphasises the close ties between China, Taiwan, and India. Additionally, Malaysia connects Saudi Arabia, Jordan, and South Africa, making it another crucial link. With various nations playing crucial roles in linking disparate areas, this map graphically highlights the global character of research cooperation.

Table 4. highlights the co-authorship analysis in bibliometric research by demonstrating the contributions of various countries to fintech and sustainability literature. China leads in both total citations (373) and average citations per article (33.91), specifying significant influence and alliance in this field. Taiwan, the UAE, and South Korea also reveal strong co-authorship networks with high average citation values, reflecting stirring contributions despite a small number of documents. Countries like the United Kingdom and Malaysia contribute more documents but have adequately lower average citations, suggesting broader but less intensive influence. Conversely, countries like Pakistan and Germany, with fewer documents and citations, indicate appearing but limited collaborative efforts in this domain. This analysis emphasizes the importance of co-authorship networks in driving impressive research and advancing knowledge in fintech and sustainability.

Table 4: Co- authorship of countries

Counties	Documents	Citation	Total link strength	Average Citation per Article
United kingdom	10	162	17	33.92
Malaysia	8	110	13	32.17
china	11	373	11	31.51
Italy	5	32	10	24.00
Pakistan	3	6	7	23.71
Germany	3	21	6	16.20
Jordan	7	166	6	13.75
South korea	5	120	5	7.10
Taiwan	6	193	4	6.41
UAE	4	126	4	2.00

Figure 5: Co-authorship countries network, source - VOSviewer

C) Citation analysis

a) Top cited Authors

Citation analysis is a technique that looks at how frequently academic publications, authors, or journals are mentioned in other works to evaluate their impact, influence, and significance. It assists in assessing the impact of a publication in its subject and acts as a quantitative indicator of academic communication. This bibliometric network (Figure 6)

connects a wide range of scholars and highlights the yield of 256 authors. Ellili, Nejla Ould Daoud, as a key figure. In several clusters of co-authorships, Ellili acts as the primary link between writers such as Kauffman, Robert J., Hoffmann, Christian Hugo, and Bui, Thi Dat. Although these co-authors are not necessarily related to one another, the network demonstrates that they collaborate directly with Ellili, suggesting that Ellili participates in distinct, autonomous research collaborations. This demonstrates a wide range of interdisciplinary contributions to different subjects. Table 5. presents a citation analysis in bibliometric research, highlighting key authors contributing to fintech and sustainability literature. The analysis discloses notable disparities in research productivity and impact among authors. **(Kauffman et al., 2017)**. leads with the highest number of articles (348), total citations (10,484), and an extraordinary H-index of 54, demonstrating both productive output and significant influence in the field.

Similarly, **(Lutfi et al., 2021) A.** reveals a high research impact with 117 articles, 3,052 citations, and an H-index of 38, reflecting sustained contributions from the UAE. On the other hand, authors like **(Deng et al., 2019)** (19 articles, 360 citations, H-index 8) and **(Naveed et al.,2017)** (10 articles, 434 citations, H-index 9) display emerging influence with moderate research outputs and citation impacts, signifying niche but growing contributions. **(Puschmann T et al.,2020)**. (37 articles, 1,313 citations, H-index 13) and **(Udeagha, M.C. et al., 2023)** (28 articles, 1,165 citations, H-index 22) illustrate well-established researchers with consistent impacts, particularly in Switzerland and South Africa, respectively.

Table 5: Top cited Authors

Author	Articles	Total citation	H- index	country	Affiliation
Abdul-Rahim, R.	59	590	13	Malaysia	Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia , Bangi, Malaysia
Najib, M.	46	637	15	Indonesia	IPB University, Bogor, Indonesia
Deng, Xiang	19	360	8	China	Sichuan University Chengdu, China
Udeagha, M.C.	28	1165	22	South Africa	University of Pretoria, Gauteng, South Africa
Zhao, Q	17	846	9	China	Research Center for County Industrial Digitalization, China
Puschmann, T.	37	1313	13	Switzerland	Universität Zürich, Switzerland
Saraji, M.K.	25	594	13	Lithuania	Vilniaus Universitetas, Vilnius, Lithuania
Naveed, K.	10	434	9	Finland	University of Jyväskylä, Jyvaskyla, Finland
Kauffman, R.J.	348	10484	54	Singapore	Singapore Management University, Singapore City, Singapore
Lutfi, A.	117	3052	38	United Arab Emirates	The University of Kalba, United Arab Emirates

Figure 6: Citation analysis of Authors, Source - VOS viewer

b) Most Cited Documents

Table 6. lists the ten most frequently referenced papers. This translates to a minimum requirement of 50 citations per publication. Results in 10 out of 70 publications. The highly cited articles showcase significant developments in the domains of technical innovation, sustainability, and fintech. With 126 citations, (Deng, X. et al., 2019) take the top spot. China's increasing impact in the industry is reflected in their work, which focuses on the connection between fintech and sustainable development.

The importance of financial and technical innovation is underlined in studies such as (Rolffs et al., 2015 and Zhao et al., 2022) from China and (2021) from the UK, both of which have 100 citations. With an amazing Field-Weighted Citation Impact (FWCI) of 27.65, (Udeghe et al., 2023) from South Africa stand out despite having 69 citations, demonstrating its strong influence.

The table highlights the worldwide focus on fintech-driven sustainability and digital transformation by showcasing a variety of contributions from economies in Asia, Europe, and the BRICS. Figure 7. shows the density visualization of top cited documents.

Table 6: Most cited Articles

Article	Theme	Total citation	country	Field-Weighted Citation impact
Deng,X.et.al 2019	FinTech and sustainable development	126	china	3.15
Rolffs, et.al 2021	Beyond technology and finance	101	United kingdom	4.93
Zhao, Q et.al .2022	financial service innovation, enhancing China's banking industry	100	China	4.69
Puschmann,et,al 2020	green fintech can alleviate the impact of climate change	80	Switzerland	3.56
Saraji. Et.al 2021	industry 4.0 adoption for a sustainable digital transformation	76	Greece	5.95
Udeagha et,al 2023	drivers of environmental sustainability in BRICS economies	69	South Africa	27.65
Naveed Et.al	sustainable growth of music industry	65	Austria	3.07
Najib.et.al 2021	Fintech in the small food business	63	Indonesia	8.88
Abdul-Rahim et.al 2022	Risk Perceptions of FinTech Adoption for Sustainability	62	Malaysia	7.54
Lutfi et.al 2023	Digital financial inclusion sustainability	58	Jordan	4.46

Figure 7: Top cited documents, Source - VOS viewer

D) Co- citation analysis of references

Figure 8. shows that the co-citation analysis identifies three groups of interrelated references, each indicating a thematic emphasis or academic debate. The first cluster

(blue) focuses on fundamental studies in financial technologies (FinTech) and their integration into economic systems, with an emphasis on their role in increasing financial inclusion. The second cluster (red) is on academic conversations around financial system sustainability and innovation, with a particular emphasis on the growth of sustainable accounting procedures and the transformational influence of technologies such as blockchain and artificial intelligence. The third cluster (green) focuses on multidisciplinary FinTech techniques, including applications in investment management and corporate governance. The connection between these clusters reflects overlapping subjects, indicating the dynamic nature of financial study.

Table 7. shows an analysis of the most frequently cited references in FinTech research, with a focus on sustainability. It highlights the number of citations and total link strength, a measure of the coupling and influence of these works within the network. **(Deng et al., 2019)** study on FinTech and sustainable development emerges as the most cited reference (**7 citations**) with the highest link strength (**22**), indicating its leading role in shaping the research field. Similarly, **(Puschmann et al., 2020)** exploration of green FinTech holds strong relevance with **5 citations** and a link strength of **21**, indicating its influence in discussions on the environmental impact of financial technologies. Works by authors like **(Moro-Visconti et al., 2020 and Anagnostopoulos et al., 2018)** show compatible engagement, with **4 citations each** and high link strengths (**18 and 16**, respectively), emphasizing their significance in sustainability and managerial impacts. The table also represents emerging themes like digital entrepreneurship **(Hommel et al.,2020)** and FinTech innovations **(Kabluova et al., 2020)**, which, in spite of fewer citations (**3–4**), exhibit substantial link strengths (**14–15**), reflecting growing academic interest. The table underscores a deeply connected network of influential studies that drive key discussions on the intersection of FinTech, sustainability, and innovation.

Table 7: Most cited references

Cited Reference	Citations	Total Link Strength
Deng X., Huang Z., Cheng X., Fintech and Sustainable Development	7	22
Puschmann T., Hoffmann C.H., Khmarskyi V., How Green is Fintech?	5	21
Moro-Visconti R., Cruz Rambaud S., Lopez Pascual J., Sustainability in Fintech	4	18
Anagnostopoulos I., Fintech and RegTech: Impact on Regulation	4	16
Chueca Vergara C., Ferruz Agudo L., Fintech and Sustainability	4	15
Gomber P., Kauffman R.J., Parker C., Weber B.W., On the Future of Fintech	4	15
Hommel K., Bican P.M., Digital Entrepreneurship in Fintech	4	14
Kabluova J., Stankeviciene J., Valuation of Fintech Innovations	3	14
Ryu H.-S., Ko K.S., Sustainable Development of Fintech	3	10
Arner D.W., Buckley R.P., Zetzsche D.A., Veidt R., Sustainability in Financial Systems	3	10

Figure 8: Co-citation analysis of references, Source - VOS viewer

E) Bibliographic sources

Table 8. represents outlines a bibliographic source list acquired from a bibliometric analysis, showcasing various academic journals and the corresponding number of articles under review. The data suggests a varied range of sources in the fields of economics, finance, sustainability, and project management, among others. The journal "Sustainability (Switzerland)" is distinct with the highest number of articles under review (5), indicating its prominent role in the field of sustainability. Other significant sources include the "International Journal of Sustainable Development and Planning" and the "Journal of Project Management (Canada)," with 2 articles each, referring to ongoing research within the country of development and project management. The remaining journals, such as the "Journal of Innovation Economics and Management," "Finance: Theory and Practice," and "Journal of Risk and Financial Management," contribute fewer articles (1 each). Overall, the spread of articles across various journals highlights the multi-disciplinary nature of the research topics being explored, with a clear focus on sustainability, financial management, and economic innovation.

Table 8: Bibliographic sources

S.no	Bibliographic sources	Articles in review
1	Journal of Innovation Economics and Management	1
2	Finance: Theory and Practice	1
3	Sustainability (Switzerland)	5
4	International Journal of Economics and Business Administration	1
5	International Journal of Sustainable Development and Planning	2
6	Focaal	1
7	Journal of Project Management (Canada)	2
8	Journal of Risk and Financial Management	1
9	European Business Organization Law Review	1
10	Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity	2
11	Investment Management and Financial Innovations	2
12	Asian Economic and Financial Review	1
13	Computer Law and Security Review	1
14	International Journal of Business and Society	1
15	Technological Forecasting and Social Change	1

Table 9: Studies highlighting relationship between Fintech and Sustainability

Title	Author	Major Findings
Sustainable Finance Meets FinTech: Amplifying Green Credit's Benefits for Banks	Zhitao Li et al., 2024	The study explores FinTech's impact on green credit performance in Chinese commercial banks from 2007-2022, finding it significantly enhances performance through cost savings, reputation enhancement, and risk mitigation, particularly in city banks and during industrial downturns.
Fintech Service Quality of Saudi Banks: Digital Transformation and Awareness in Satisfaction, Re-Use Intentions, and the Sustainable Performance of Firms	Aldaarmi et al., 2024	The study investigates the relationship between fintech service quality, customer happiness, and long-term bank performance in Saudi Arabian banks, and finds no significant link between digital awareness and satisfaction.
The Impact of the Omnibus Low Cipta Kerja on the Sustainability of MSMEs and Economic Growth by Applying the Canvas Model Business Method and the Use of Financial Technology, Especially Crowdfunding and Microfinance	Hadi et al., 2023	The study explores the impact of the omnibus low cipta kerja on the sustainability of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in Indonesia. It highlights the government's policies, including technology finance, crowdfunding, and the Business Model Canvas, which provide advantages like a single license, incentives, and legal assistance.
Green FinTech Innovation as a Future Research Direction: A Bibliometric Analysis on Green Finance and FinTech	Kwong et al., 2023	This paper analyzes research on green finance and FinTech up to 2022, focusing on the investment and application aspects. It suggests future research directions include a greater focus on the regulatory environment in developing countries, a more comprehensive understanding of the investment aspect of green finance, and a more focused focus on Green FinTech research.
Investigating the Impact of Financial Inclusion Drivers, Financial Literacy and Financial Initiatives in Fostering Sustainable Growth in North India	Pandey et al., 2022	The study examines the impact of financial inclusion drivers, financial literacy, and financial initiatives on sustainable growth, revealing usage, digitalization, and FinTech as significant drivers, with financial literacy playing a crucial role.
Sustainable fintech innovation orientation: A moderated model	Al-Okaily et al., 2021	The study examines the factors influencing FinTech acceptance in Jordan, focusing on social, environmental, and ecological benefits. Results show perceived usefulness and enjoyment significantly influence users' decisions, with eWOM moderated.
Regulating Sustainable Finance in the Dark	Zetsche et al., 2022	The EU Sustainable Finance Strategy highlights deficiencies in sustainability-oriented financial regulation, including lack of sustainability data, theoretical insights, and inconsistent application of rules. These will be addressed with the implementation of the EU's sustainability taxonomy, taxonomy-based reporting, and smart regulation tools.
Do fintech, natural resources and globalization matter during ecological crises? A step towards ecological sustainability	Okere et al., 2024	The Load Capacity Curve framework reveals a negative correlation between natural resource rents and globalization in the North African region, while Fintech positively impacts environmental sustainability, suggesting a bidirectional causality.

5. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Despite offering insightful information on the relationship between fintech and sustainability, the review has limitations. One of the significant restrictions is the scope of the literature search. The search query was broad, but because it had general phrases like "fintech" and "sustainability" in titles, abstracts, and keywords, it could have missed more focused studies that investigate aspects of fintech within sustainable finance or other relevant fields. Additionally, the number of publications from Q1 and Q2 Scopus journals was low, most likely due to the fact that this problem is still rather new and there isn't currently a lot of high-impact, peer-reviewed research. Since it limited the breadth and depth of outstanding research that could be looked at, this could have impacted the legitimacy of the conclusions drawn. Furthermore, the review only sourced publications from the Scopus database, leaving out pertinent research from other significant academic databases, including Google Scholar, IEEE Xplore, and the Web of Science. Studies in different databases may provide a variety of regional insights, interdisciplinary approaches, or alternative methodological frameworks that would improve the analysis, so limiting the search to Scopus may prevent the review from capturing the entire spectrum of fintech and sustainability research that is available.

5.1 Future research directions

Investment Strategies in Green Finance: Investigate how fintech can enhance green investment opportunities, focusing on sustainable financial products and services (Kwong et al., 2023)

Integration of Fintech in Banking Systems: Study how traditional banking institutions can incorporate fintech solutions to promote sustainable practices and products (Liu et al. 2024)

Sustainable Financial Inclusion: Analyze how fintech can provide access to financial services for underserved populations while promoting environmental sustainability (Arshi et al., 2024)

Advancing Sustainable Finance: Less is known about how fintech and sustainable practices interact, which presents a wealth of opportunities for further study that may show how fintech innovations help to achieve more general environmental and social goals (Macchiavello & Siri, 2022).

Strengthening Corporate Governance: Future studies could explore fintech's role in detecting fraud, strengthening corporate governance practices, increasing profitability, and contributing to corporate sustainability goals (Najaf, K., Chin 2024).

Fostering Technological Innovation: Fintech-driven financial innovations reduce agency costs and risks, which helps businesses increase economic growth and efficiency. Research into how fintech facilitates technological advancements can reveal insights into how businesses gain competitive advantages, enhance financial performance, and bolster sustainability efforts. These studies would demonstrate how fintech is revolutionising the financial industry by promoting innovation (Li et al., 2020).

6. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This study contributes to our understanding of the multifaceted relationship between fintech, financial performance, and sustainability through a comprehensive bibliometric analysis. By examining scholarly literature indexed in the Scopus database, we identified key themes, influential studies, and emerging areas within this dynamic field. The results show that by encouraging green financing, lowering information asymmetry, and increasing small investors' access to investment possibilities, fintech may propel sustainable finance. By providing innovative ideas for energy management, environmentally friendly transportation, and public involvement, fintech also aids in the creation of sustainable smart cities. According to the bibliometric analysis, the topic at the nexus of sustainability and fintech continues to expand quickly, as evidenced by the significant increase in publications, teamwork, and worldwide contributions between 2015 and 2024. The high citation average and 37.87% per year growth rate demonstrate the increasing interest of scholars in this field.

Though productivity peaked in 2022, the current modest dip might be attributed to changes in research priorities or market saturation. This dataset offers a thorough overview of the development of the discipline, including significant figures and international research trends. As seen in Figure 4, the prevalence of terms such as "sustainability," "FinTech," and "finance" highlights sustainability as a major area of focus for study. Strong international cooperation is demonstrated by the co-authorship network in Figure 5, wherein nations such as the UK, China, and Malaysia serve as important nodes connecting different research hubs. Figure 6. Citation analysis highlights a variety of multidisciplinary contributions by distinguishing significant writers, particularly Ellili, who combines several co-authorship clusters.

In closing, Figure 8, the co-citation network, displays theme clusters that link disciplines such as risk management, sustainability, and digital finance, demonstrating the field's multidisciplinary reach and cooperation. These observations provide an in-depth analysis of the field of study and identify key figures and themes in international academic networks. A number of important topics have emerged from the convergence of sustainability and financial technology (fintech), each of which shows how important a role fintech can play in advancing sustainable development. Sustainable finance, which looks at how fintech technologies support green funding and more open, responsible ESG (environmental, social, and governance) reporting, is one of the main themes.

Fintech can improve the transparency required for sustainable investing strategies by providing more access to real-time data and analytics, assisting investors in making well-informed choices that support social and environmental objectives. Another important issue is financial inclusion and access, which focuses on how fintech products like peer-to-peer lending and mobile banking can provide financial services to underprivileged groups. By creating possibilities in underserved communities, this expanded access to financial resources promotes more equitable economic growth and advances social sustainability.

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